

30-Sentabr, 2024-Yil

MUSIC PEDAGOGY IN A PRESCHOOL EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTION

Shamurodova Medina

Republic of Karakalpakstan.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13825118>

Abstract. This article talks about the history, theory and methodology of music pedagogy, music education system in preschool educational institutions.

Key words: music pedagogy, education, musical sounds.

МУЗЫКАЛЬНАЯ ПЕДАГОГИКА В ДОШКОЛЬНОМ ОБРАЗОВАТЕЛЬНОМ
УЧРЕЖДЕНИИ.

Аннотация. В статье рассказывается об истории, теории и методике музыкальной педагогики, системе музыкального образования в дошкольных образовательных учреждениях.

Ключевые слова: музыкальная педагогика, образование, музыкальные звуки.

Music pedagogy - studies the history, theory and methodology of the music education system. Of course, without knowing how the theory and practice of musical education and training of the young generation has progressed, it is impossible to scientifically solve the issues of their spiritual education. Music pedagogy was formed and developed in connection with the history of our nation's culture.

After all, the history of Uzbek music culture is the basis of music pedagogy. Music pedagogy as a social science approaches the events of historical pedagogy based on the needs of the times. It clarifies that the theory, practice, and content of musical education differed at different stages of the period, it shows the socio-cultural essence of advanced musical-educational views and the path of development.

The main goal of music education and upbringing in preschool educational institutions is to form the worldview of children from the kindergarten age and to develop their musical taste, and in the process of teaching music to children, it means that life is reflected in it. It should be noted that in order to realize the pedagogical goals and tasks set before music lessons, first of all, it is necessary to regularly develop children's musical skills and abilities.

Children's musical learning and abilities consist of the following activities: - musical learning (the ability to feel the loudness and lowness of musical sounds); - timbre reading (distinguishing musical sounds from each other); - a sense of rhythm (moving to the music,

30-Sentabr, 2024-Yil

keeping the music in memory, feeling and expressing it by stepping and clapping). Children's musical abilities develop regularly during the implementation of all elements of musical training.

The main tasks of music education in kindergartens are as follows:

- developing children's interest in music;
- to enrich children's ideas about music by creating emotional feelings in the process of introducing them to musical works;
 - to develop children's creative abilities with the help of listening to music, singing, performing rhythmic movements to music, accompanying children's musical instruments;
 - nurturing children's voices, teaching and accustoming them to sing songs simply, fluently, freely, naturally and expressively;
 - to enjoy musical works, to develop musical taste and artistic thinking on this basis;
 - teaching to express the artistic images of the musical work in the form of games and dances during music lessons;
 - introducing children to our national values in music lessons, teaching them to perform national musical and rhythmic movements accompanied by national musical instruments;
- connecting the content of music classes with kindergarten life, participating in kindergarten events with learned tunes and songs. Organization of special mornings and concerts.

During music lessons, the child perceives life and surroundings through musical images.

In the kindergarten, musical education is carried out in an integral connection with fiction and visual arts. Every music lesson conducted using special methods arouses artistic and aesthetic pleasure in children, shapes their feelings, develops creative thinking and speech. In addition, musical games and dances help children develop a sense of rhythm, agility and mobility skills, and help them grow properly. It is important for the child's mental and physical development. All musical educational and educational activities carried out in pre-school educational institutions are considered to be a component of education of refinement in the formation of noble qualities in the young generation from the kindergarten age.

Music is a reflection of life, reality and time, as well as expressing human feelings.

Therefore, the main criterion in the principles of the music program is "Music and life".

Scientists of music pedagogy say - "In the process of learning music, students easily feel and understand that life is reflected in it, and that they learn life through it." Based on the students' life experiences, an understanding is given that each piece of music reflects a certain reality, feelings and thoughts. This is done only by perceiving the work and its images while performing various musical activities during the lesson. After all, no matter what musical activity we take in

30-Sentabr, 2024-Yil

a lesson, it is carried out positively after first perceiving the sound of music and understanding its image and characters.

Therefore, music perception is the main factor of the learning process. Therefore, to hear music, to enjoy it, to sing, to understand the characteristics of music literacy, to dance, to perform various rhythmic movements to the sound of music, to clap and play instruments, to accompany the music rhythmically. activities such as perceiving can be performed. Music perception in the lesson in two ways - special hearing of musical works (listening to music) and listening and understanding music and performing various activities in accordance with its character. Today, in the lesson of modern music culture, music perception plays an important role as a leading activity.

It is done in two cases:

1. a certain work is listened to and perceived, and its artistic descriptions are analyzed in a simple musical-pedagogical way related to the subject of the lesson. Understanding and conscious perception of the work through hearing, gaining certain knowledge about the musical features (genre, structure, means of expression, performance) and artistic content of the work.

2. Musical works are studied by students by listening (perceiving) them carefully, and then by singing this or that activity more. The features of its artistic content are expressed in practical activities. For example, the song to be learned is first listened to by the teacher (also on CD) a couple of times, the features of the piece are discussed, and then the study is started. Dance music is first listened to, after understanding the description of the melody, the expression of dance movements is studied. Often, the work is studied in combination of several activities (listening, singing, dance movements, etc.).

This method of training provides an opportunity for a thorough study of the work and at the same time for the development of complex skills. In the lesson of music culture, all activities are logically interconnected under a certain topic. As a result, a logical unity of the lesson is created. Music literacy is important as a theoretical unifying activity of all activities. No matter what type of activity (listening, singing, dancing, etc.) is used in the lesson, the work used in its practice is studied and new concepts are formed about its features (genre, structure, performance, etc.).

REFERENCES

1. Зими́на А. Основы музыкального воспитания и развития. Москва, Владос, 2000.
2. Norxo'jayev N. O'zbekiston Vatanim manim. T.1999.

• ZAMONAVIY ILM-FAN VA TA'LIM ISTIQBOLLARI •
ILMIY-AMALIY KONFERENSIYASI

30-Sentabr, 2024-Yil

3. Школяр Л. В, Школяр В.А, Критская Е.Д. и др. Музыкальное образование в школе. Москва, 2001.
4. Hasanboyeva O., Hasanboev J., Homidov £. Pedagogika tarixi. Tos'hkent, G'.G'ulom, 2004.
5. Begmatov S. va boshqalar "Musiqa" 6 - sinf. Toshkent, G'.G'ulom, 2003

MODERN SCIENCE
& RESEARCH